

Feature based wound healing prediction through Machine Learning approach

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Abstract

The medical study evaluation of wound healing is critical. Traditional wound healing evaluation methods usually rely on subjective visual inspections, which are time-consuming and susceptible to human error. So, the current work presents a machine learning framework for predicting wound healing status based on features extracted from wound images. Using a dataset of improved wound pictures, we assessed the efficacy of several classification algorithms. Following feature scaling, algorithms including Random Forest, Support Vector Machine (SVM), k-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), AdaBoost, Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, and XGBoost were tested and trained. Classification metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score were employed to evaluate the models. SVM achieved the highest accuracy of up to 88.57% with 100% precision when compared to the algorithms used in this study. The Flask web application was used to implement the model for real-time wound healing prediction.

Keywords

Machine Learning, Wound, Dataset, Web Application, Prediction.

1. Introduction

Wound healing is a complicated biological process; medical interventions can be made more quickly by anticipating how a wound would heal. The progress of wound healing may be quantified by the rate of change of the wound's surface area [12]. However, this is a challenging task due to the complexity of the wound, variable lighting conditions, and the time constraints in clinical laboratories. Patients who experience traumatic pain may worry and experience anxiety, and in extreme cases, this can result in depression [14]. Chronic wounds also require continued care to prevent infection since they heal slowly, and the cost of ongoing diagnosis and treatment of these wounds is significant for both the individual and the community. Wound measurements can be carried out in a variety of

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techniques, however in order to compare outcomes of studies, a consistent technique must be used each time [10]. Many commercially available wound measuring cameras that use inbuilt algorithms for assessing wound size are available [3,16], due to their high cost, not all clinics or research facilities have access to them. Wounds are typically classified manually by professionals and recorded in the electronic health record (EHR). Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been widely used in healthcare, including drug discovery, eye care, and medical image diagnostic systems [6]. AI systems have shifted from rule-based to data-driven methodologies, eliminating the need for human interaction. AI techniques, such as Machine Learning (ML), are used in a variety of healthcare fields, including ophthalmology, immunology, genetics, and wound care [5]. These machine learning techniques enable clinicians to monitor the healing process over time and forecast wound healing status. Predictive machine learning algorithms use patient data to assess wound healing potential and generate individualized treatment regimens. Furthermore, machine learning (ML) has demonstrated efficacy in more precisely tracking the healing process, determining wound size, and segmenting wound areas in photos. These models aid in identifying problems early on, improving patient outcomes, and informing clinical decision-making.

Image processing and machine learning techniques are used to automatically assess wound healing status by assessing features retrieved from images. The research aims to use machine learning-based algorithms to predict healing status, resulting in a more automated, objective, and efficient process than past approaches[8]. This application focuses on the combination of medical imaging with machine learning, which has the potential to improve clinical decision-making, reduce subjectivity in assessments, and streamline wound care management. A real-time wound healing application uses Flask, a Python micro web framework, to facilitate image processing, machine learning, and data management[13]. As digital cameras and cell phones become more widely available, the process of capturing wound photographs is gaining in popularity and ease. As a result, these devices are being utilized more frequently to record and track the healing process of wounds. The present work intends to create a system that can more accurately predict wound healing stages of a patient by combining the findings of various machine learning algorithms and integrating them with a web app that allows the user to assess their probability of healing of wound in real time

2. Method

2.1 Data Collection

The dataset used in the study was obtained from the [18]. The images taken were from day 0 to day 15, there were 255 total original pictures of healing stages of wounds with four time points. The MS-SSIM (Multi Scale- Structural Similarity Index Measure) has been used to separate them into categories for progressed healing and non-healing. Then, the healed class was created as a minority class. Thus, we have enhanced 95 images to create a total of 350 Images.

2.2 Feature Extraction and Data Preprocessing

To improve the quality and concentrate on pertinent details, preprocessing the wound healing images is crucial before feature extraction. In order to reduce computing complexity, the following pre-

processing techniques are used: standardizing the size of the wound images to a consistent dimension (e.g., 256x256 pixels). To eliminate noise that can obstruct feature extraction, filters (median and Gaussian blur) were used. An image area, mean intensity, Hu moments (texture values ranging from 0 to 3), RGB color pixel values, and other crucial characteristics are used to assess progress of healing of wound. All of these extracted features (Comma Separated Values) were stored in a CSV file format. We removed unnecessary columns and then used StandardScaler to normalize the feature values such that each feature would have a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1. This was necessary to increase the machine learning models' efficiency. The scikit-learn train test split function was utilized to partition the dataset into training (80%) and testing (20%) sets.

2.3 Apply Machine Learning

Data can be categorized into distinct classes based on specific characteristics, enabling classification models to be constructed from historical records and sample data. A primary objective of categorization is to enhance the consistency and reliability of data-driven predictions [6]. Once the data is pre-processed and structured, machine learning techniques can be applied effectively. In the present study, we employ various classification and ensemble methods to predict wound healing stages accurately. Ensemble techniques, which aggregate predictions from multiple models, are often constructed by manipulating the input data for individual classifiers [11]. A common approach involves generating a training set through bootstrapping, where samples are randomly selected with replacement from the original dataset to train each model variant. The overarching goal of using machine learning techniques in this context is twofold: to evaluate the predictive accuracy of each model in wound healing assessment and to identify the most influential features that play a critical role in the classification outcomes. By pinpointing these key features, the model not only becomes interpretable but also enables more targeted and effective healthcare interventions based on the stages of wound healing.

2.4 Algorithms used

RANDOM FOREST- Random Forest is an approach for bootstrapping and ensemble composition that might help to minimize overfitting [1]. **SVM-** SVM is a supervised machine learning technique that surpasses other machine learning algorithms and has been thoroughly evaluated in real-world classification problems and nonlinear function forecasting tasks [17]. **KNN-** this method is utilized for both classification and regression. The primary goal of this algorithm is to categorize new objects based on their properties and training examples [15]. This algorithm predicts the level of the test sample based on the k training samples, which are the closest neighbours to the test individual, and returns the result with the highest-level probability [7]. **LOGISTIC REGRESSION-** Logistic Regression is a classification approach based on the concept of probability that can be utilized in predictive analytics. It is used to resolve categorization issues. This approach produces a discrete binary result between 0 and 1 [8]. **DECISION TREE:** For wound healing prediction, relevant features such as wound area, texture, Color intensity, and edge sharpness were extracted from the images. These features were normalized to ensure consistency and reduce variability, enabling the Decision Tree to

effectively partition the data based on meaningful distinctions among wound healing stages. AdaBoost improves accuracy by focusing on cases that previous models misclassified, thereby refining the classifier's ability to identify wound stages accurately. AdaBoost's adaptability to complex data distributions makes it suitable for wound healing prediction, where image-based features often vary in subtle and nuanced ways. We applied XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting), a scalable and efficient machine learning algorithm well-suited for classification tasks with high-dimensional and complex data, to predict wound healing stages.

2.5 Model Training and Evaluation:

Every model was tested on the test set (X_{test} , Y_{test}) after being trained on the training set (X_{train} , Y_{train}). Performance indicators such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score were computed to assess the model's efficacy. A confusion matrix was generated as well so that the classification performance of each model could be easily assessed. To enable real-time prediction in the future, the models were additionally serialized and saved using joblib. In order to predict the state of wound healing, a variety of machine learning models were trained and assessed for this research. An ensemble of decision trees was constructed using the Random Forest Classifier, and its accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score were evaluated. Key predictors were revealed by examining the feature importance. The best hyperplane for class separation was found using the Support Vector Machine (SVM), which performed better when alternative kernels and regularization parameters were used. By maximizing the number of neighbors and distance metric, the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) model which is based on majority vote among the nearest neighbors was improved. Through the use of a logistic function and regularization to reduce overfitting, logistic regression was utilized to estimate binary outcomes.

Recursively dividing the input, the Decision Tree Classifier created a tree structure and showed its decision-making process. AdaBoost enhanced predictions on challenging samples by combining adaptive weighting with weak learners, while the XGBoost Classifier used sophisticated gradient boosting methods together with hyperparameter tuning to attain high accuracy. Metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score were used to assess each model's performance on the test dataset; cross-validation was optional to guarantee robustness. Plotting confusion matrices allowed for the visualization of prediction results, and feature importance analysis allowed for the understanding of the effects of various features. The best-performing model was chosen with the use of model comparison and hyperparameter modification. A thorough record of the findings and observations allowed for a clear comprehension of the advantages and disadvantages of each model.

2.6 Web Application

To make our wound healing prediction model accessible and user-friendly, we developed a web application using the Flask framework, a lightweight and widely used web development framework in Python. The goal of this application is to provide clinicians with real-time access to our machine learning model's predictions, offering a practical tool for wound assessment and monitoring. The machine learning model that achieved the highest accuracy was selected and saved as a serialized

file using Python's pickle library. By saving the model as a .pkl file, we enable efficient loading and use of the model in a web environment without needing to retrain or reload the model from scratch each time the web service is accessed. This approach optimizes response time and ensures consistent, reproducible predictions.

3. Results and Discussion:

The goal of this study was to employ feature analysis to assess the rate of wound healing in surface wounds. Monitoring wound conditions over time is a crucial aspect of wound care, which is currently performed manually [2]. The development of a computer-based wound monitoring system will enable the establishment of standard wound healing rates, the reduction of inter- and intra-observer variances, and the electronic storage and retrieval of this data as part of the patient's medical record. In a pilot study [9], only 255 images from four time points and a limited collection of texture properties and geometrical metrics were used to assess the proposed technique. The structural similarity image quality model suggests that the human visual system is well-suited to collecting structural information from a scene, thus ensuring that a measure of structural similarity can provide an accurate approximation to perceived image quality. MS-SSIM, an extension of the Structural Similarity Index (SSIM), assesses the observed difference between two images. MS-SSIM is a more reliable indication of picture quality than SSIM since it assesses local image structures at many scales rather than a single scale comparison. MS-SSIM assisted us in determining the similarity rate between days 0 and 15 for all images. That means less resemblance, leading to the healing stage. So, based on this, wound images are classified as healed or not healed

(Figure 1).

Figure 1: MS- SSI assessment of the difference between two images.

Pair	MS-SSIM Score	Interpretation
Day_0_A8-3-R.png vs Day_1_A8-3-R.png	0.7169905736273173	Moderate
Day_0_A8-3-R.png vs Day_2_A8-3-R.png	0.7253174609913235	Moderate
Day_0_A8-3-R.png vs Day_3_A8-3-R.png	0.731701034435765	Moderate
Day_0_A8-3-R.png vs Day_4_A8-3-R.png	0.6232612694443578	Moderate
Day_0_A8-3-R.png vs Day_5_A8-3-R.png	0.6021091471873589	Moderate
Day_0_A8-3-R.png vs Day_6_A8-3-R.png	0.5557564005991285	Moderate
Day_0_A8-3-R.png vs Day_7_A8-3-R.png	0.5586473626630394	Moderate
Day_0_A8-3-R.png vs Day_8_A8-3-R.png	0.3839495352408395	Low
Day_0_A8-3-R.png vs Day_9_A8-3-R.png	0.4466084219261539	Low
Day_0_A8-3-R.png vs Day_10_A8-3-R.png	0.48361266003289616	Low
Day_0_A8-3-R.png vs Day_11_A8-3-R.png	0.49662229073891484	Low
Day_0_A8-3-R.png vs Day_12_A8-3-R.png	0.46166552879568534	Low
Day_0_A8-3-R.png vs Day_13_A8-3-R.png	0.4350775258381784	Low
Day_0_A8-3-R.png vs Day_14_A8-3-R.png	0.4704798496068143	Low
Day_0_A8-3-R.png vs Day_15_A8-3-R.png	0.4802252395372788	Low

The precision identifies the model's accuracy in predicting specific wound stages, which is crucial to avoid misclassifying a wound as more severe than it is, leading to overtreatment. The recall reflects the model's sensitivity, particularly important to ensure that wounds in early or critical stages are not missed. High recall in wound classification implies the model's efficacy in capturing relevant cases, which is essential for timely medical interventions. The F1-score provides a balanced view of the

model's accuracy and is particularly useful when there's a class imbalance (e.g., fewer images of severe wounds compared to minor wounds).

The performance assessment of these machine learning models reveals clear strengths and limitations among various classifiers, providing insight into their suitability for different application priorities, such as accuracy, precision, or recall. Overall, the performance evaluation of the machine learning models reveals that SVM achieved the highest accuracy of 88.57% and flawless precision of 100%, indicating an exceptional ability to correctly identify relevant instances with zero false negatives (**Figure 2**). The high accuracy and perfect precision of SVM suggest it is highly effective in detecting relevant wound healing stages with minimal false positives. An accurate model can help clinicians make reliable assessments about the healing stage, supporting appropriate treatment. High precision is essential for preventing overtreatment or under treatment. Such that, a false positive prediction of an advanced healing stage might lead clinicians to decrease treatment prematurely, risking patient health. Berezoet, al.,[4] demonstrates that machine learning models can effectively predict chronic wound healing time by leveraging historical clinical data from real-world patient records. By identifying patients at elevated risk of delayed or non-healing wounds, these models provide clinicians with a proactive tool for early intervention and tailored treatment planning, potentially improving patient outcomes and resource allocation in wound management. This makes SVM particularly suitable for applications where incorrect classifications could lead to misinformed clinical decisions. In another study[12], a Support Vector Machine classifier (SVM) was used to segment wound tissue and retrieve the contour. The authors trained their approach using 50 photos manually demarcated by specialists before testing it on 23 fresh images of wounds. The SVM system accurately classified 94% of pixels as wound or non-wound, compared to hand tracings by experts. In the present study, the increase in the number of images, an SVM model could reliably distinguish between different wound healing stages, reducing the risk of over- or under-treating a wound. KNN excels in recall (83.72%) with an accuracy of 85.71%, meaning high recall rate signifies its ability to capture true positives effectively. In wound healing, this is advantageous when the goal is to ensure all potential wound features or stages are detected, which can be crucial for comprehensive monitoring. Although KNN has a slightly lower precision than SVM, it can serve as a reliable choice in scenarios where missing any relevant wound characteristics would be detrimental to patient outcomes.

XGBoost achieved similar accuracy to Logistic Regression (84.29%) but showed a slight advantage in recall, meaning it slightly favors capturing true positives. XGBoost shows a balanced performance between recall and precision, making it a robust option for applications requiring both sensitivity and specificity. Its adaptability could be beneficial for wound images with varying textures, colors, and shapes associated with different healing phases. XGBoost's interpretability also supports clinical applications, enabling healthcare providers to understand which image features contribute most to the model's decisions. Logistic Regression's consistent accuracy makes it a dependable, interpretable model for straightforward classification tasks. In wound healing, Logistic Regression could effectively classify wound images into distinct categories (e.g., stages of healing) with reasonable accuracy. Its interpretability is particularly valuable in medical settings,

where transparent decision-making is often required (**Table 1**). Both Random Forest and AdaBoost provide stable generalization, which can be beneficial when analyzing wound images from diverse patient populations or varied imaging conditions. Their robustness against overfitting makes them practical for wound datasets with high variability in wound size, appearance, and environmental factors affecting image quality. The Decision Tree's lower accuracy reflects its limitations in complex classification tasks but remains valuable for its simplicity and efficiency. In a wound-healing, a Decision Tree model could be utilized in preliminary analysis or quick triage situations, offering rapid, interpretable results that can guide initial assessments. This evaluation highlights that model selection should align with specific performance metrics critical to the application context, such as prioritizing precision with SVM or maximizing recall with KNN (Figure 3). With its excellent accuracy and zero false negatives, SVM is the ideal choice for significant wound evaluation applications where misclassification could jeopardize treatment plans.

Table 1: Shows the comparison of all our models and the SVM model showed the highest accuracy.

--	DT	RF	AB	L R	XGB	KNN	S VM
TP	23	24	24	26	25	24	27
FP	13	11	11	10	09	07	08
TN	30	32	32	33	34	35	35
FN	04	03	03	01	02	03	00
A (%)	75.71	80.00	80.00	84.29	84.29	85.71	88.57
P (%)	88.24	91.43	91.43	94.44	94.44	92.31	100
R (%)	69.77	74.42	74.42	79.07	79.07	83.72	81.40
F1(%)	77.92	82.05	82.05	86.08	86.08	87.80	89.74

Figure 2: Accuracy Comparison of Machine Learning Models.

Figure 3: The confusion matrix of all 7 models has been plotted using seaborn's library to compare the performance of each model

Figure 4: The result of the prediction of wound (healed or not healed) by all the machine learning model is shown in the Web application.

Enter Features for Prediction

Pixel 0:

Pixel 1:

Pixel 2:

Texture 0:

Texture 1:

Texture 2:

Texture 3:

Area:

Mean Intensity:

Prediction Results

Model	Prediction
RandomForest	healed
SVM	healed
KNN	healed
LogisticRegression	healed
DecisionTree	not healed
AdaBoost	healed
XGBoost	not healed

[Back to Enter Features](#)

The findings in Machine Learning-Based Wound Healing Prediction have important implications for medical diagnosis and healthcare accessibility. It introduces a machine learning-based web-based application built with Flask that provides an economical and accessible way to wound healing testing, which is critical given the high cost of medical wound treatments. Users can enter health data and obtain quick predictions about their healing condition, making the diagnostic procedure easier and more accessible (Figure 4). This approach not only simplifies wound diagnosis but also improves healthcare decision-making through accurate forecasts, showing a substantial leap in the application of machine learning to health care.

4. Conclusion

Our study effectively put into practice a thorough machine learning pipeline for utilizing a variety of classification models to predict the state of wound healing. The models were successfully trained and assessed by pre-processing the picture characteristics, standardizing the data, and dividing it into training and testing sets. In order to provide real-time predictions based on user input in a Flask web application, the scaler and trained models were preserved. Through the use of an easily navigable web interface, this end-to-end method not only exhibited strong model performance but also guaranteed practical application, offering insightful information about wound healing assessments.

This paper concludes the application of machine learning for medical research where it can be a useful instrument (in wound healing assessment). With its ability to predict the healing status of wounds inaccuracy through image-derived features, this system could become an important tool for researchers and more precise wound assessment practices. The fact that the system is possible, functioning properly and successfully means model can be deployed in research settings; an important milestone for technology to actually improve healthcare or medical research.

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